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Educational Paradigms in Perspective: While Teachers and Students Evaluate Outcome-Based and Traditional Educational Approaches

Abstract: Outcome-Based Education (OBE) is a student-centric teaching approach which rejects the traditional education system that focuses on what is taught. The National Education Policy of India, 2020, considers OBE as the reformed concept of education and many higher education systems are shifting their curricula to OBE. Thus, there is a need to study how the students consider the shift from a traditional input-based teaching approach to a student-centric educational approach. Therefore, the study aims to examine the outcome-based experiential teaching experience of teachers who taught in the traditional method and the learning experiences of the students who have studied their undergraduate in a traditional methods and studying their postgraduation in the OBE curriculum at Marian College Kuttikkanam (Autonomous), Kerala, India. The study was qualitative in nature and adopted a narrative research design. Twelve teachers and twelve students from 6 postgraduate departments were purposefully selected for the study using expert analysis. The data were collected using the interview method. The collected data were analysed using thematic analysis. The study results showed that the transition to Outcome-Based Education (OBE) had significantly shifted teaching styles from teacher-focused to student-centred, emphasising specific learning outcomes, critical thinking, and practical application, despite some challenges in adaptation. The need for future research was acknowledged to facilitate this change further, examining strategies such as teacher training, technology integration, and the long-term impacts of OBE on student outcomes.

Keywords: Outcome-based education, Experiential learning, Educational paradigms, Post-graduate students, Teachers, Traditional approach

Introduction

Education, as a fundamental instrument of human progress and development, has evolved significantly over the centuries, adapting to societal changes and technological advancements (Rao, 2020). Today, the brink of another major educational revolution is being approached, marked by a shift from traditional pedagogical methods to a more student-centric, outcome-oriented approach, known as Outcome-Based Education (OBE) (Babu & Joseph, 2022). This revolution aims to transform our classrooms and mould the ethos of our

education systems (Sullivan & Downey, 2015; Bremner, 2020). In the traditional education paradigm, the focus predominantly lies on what is taught—the course content, learning resources, and standardised examinations. Its primary drawback is that it often overlooks individual learner needs and outcomes (Babu & Roy, 2023). Consequently, it has been increasingly criticised for its rigidity and lack of applicability in a rapidly evolving world (Sakata et al., 2022; Katawazai, 2021). On the contrary, OBE prioritises the abilities, skills, and knowledge students should possess upon completing their education (Rao, 2020). It emphasises defining and achieving measurable outcomes, promoting active learning, and fostering personalised and experiential education.

Against this backdrop, the National Education Policy of India (NEP), unveiled in 2020, presents a significant step towards implementing OBE in India's educational landscape (Babu & Roy, 2023). The policy envisions transforming the Indian educational system by adopting a more holistic, flexible approach that encourages multidisciplinary learning (Patnaik & Paas, 2023; Akir et al., 2012). Notably, it gives prominence to the OBE paradigm, recognising it as an indispensable element of modern education (Botha, 2002). The implementation of this policy, thus, sets the stage for a seismic shift in the educational ethos of India (Babu & Joseph, (2022)). This significant transformation presents an invaluable opportunity to explore the comparative perceptions and experiences of postgraduate teachers and students transitioning from traditional to OBE curricula. Hence, this article seeks to critically analyse the transition to OBE, delving into the perspectives of teachers and students experiencing this shift first-hand. The current study intends to investigate the differential experiences of students who have pursued their undergraduate studies under the traditional approach and are encountering the OBE curriculum in their postgraduate studies. OBE is a newly innovative educative program where very few colleges have been practicing this approach. Therefore, the significant transformation of the OBE program is important to be explored. This study examines the challenges and potential advantages that postgraduate teachers have perceived in this transition.

Methods

Research Design

This study employs a qualitative methodological approach, using a narrative research design to explore the shift from traditional input-based teaching to an outcome-based education (OBE) system. The research setting was Marian College Kuttikkanam (Autonomous) in Kerala, India, a significant educational institution that has embraced the OBE paradigm for its postgraduate curriculum. This choice of locale ensured a context-rich exploration of the topic at hand.

Sample Selection

The study's sample included 24 participants, equally divided between teachers and students, meticulously chosen from six diverse postgraduate disciplines. Selection criteria were informed by comprehensive expert review to ensure a wide range of experiences and perspectives. The teachers had at least 3 years of experience in both OBE and traditional teaching methods. Conversely, the student participants, having completed their undergraduate education within a traditional framework, were currently engaged in

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postgraduate studies under the OBE methods. This mix offered valuable insights into the comparative dynamics of the two teaching methods.

Data Collection

Data was gathered using in-depth interviews. A structured interview protocol was developed, emphasizing various dimensions of the OBE model. Topics covered included teaching strategies, study modalities, pedagogical tasks, fieldwork practices, examination methodologies, and evaluation processes. The interviews aimed to capture participants' experiences within the OBE environment and contrast these with prior academic engagements in a traditional setting during undergraduate studies.

Data Analysis

For the data analysis process, a strategy known as content analysis was put into action. This involved carefully reviewing and coding the interview transcripts to uncover recurring themes, distinct patterns, and unique perspectives on the students' experiences with the OBE curriculum. To enhance the study's integrity and mitigate potential bias, the data underwent a review by two students and two teachers. An additional verification step involved returning to the participants for cross-verification of the collected data. Content analysis technique helped navigate the data systematically, helping to pinpoint important findings about the contrast between OBE and traditional education in terms of teaching styles, academic activities, and evaluation procedures.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers ensured that ethical guidelines were strictly adhered to throughout the research. All participants voluntarily gave consent after being fully informed about the study's objectives, ensuring their voluntary participation. Anonymity and confidentiality were preserved by replacing personal identifiers with participant codes during data collection, analysis, and reporting.

Results

The study presents a diverse participant profile with a broad range of ages and educational backgrounds. The study revealed an even age distribution among its participants: half were students aged 20-23, while the other half were teachers aged 30-45. A notable gender disparity was observed, with the majority being female. Among twenty-four participants, eighteen were female - eight of whom were teachers - and six were male, including three teachers. Regarding educational qualifications, eight teachers held PhDs, while four had completed post-graduation. The twelve students are currently pursuing their postgraduate studies.

Table 1 Characteristics of the participants

Characteristics		Age
Age	20 – 23	12
	30 – 45	12
Gender	Male	6
	Female	18
Educational Qualification	PhD	8
	PG	4
	Studying PG	12

The Shift towards Traditional Teaching to OBE

Teachers Perspectives

All the teachers reported a profound shift in teaching methodology from a traditional, teacher-centred approach to a learner-centric, outcome-based model with Outcome-Based Education (OBE) implementation. The implementation of OBE has brought about significant changes in the teaching-learning process. It has shifted the focus from teacher-led, rote learning to a more student-centred, practical, and skill-oriented education. Technology integration into education has reshaped the teaching process, stimulating self-guided learning and critical thinking while transforming the evaluation of student performance. Although obstacles remain, the shift to Outcome-Based Education (OBE) seems to mould a more lively, engaging, and effective learning landscape.

Teachers have observed a substantial alteration in teaching methods, transitioning from a mostly instructor-focused model to one that centres around the learner. The emphasis has been redirected from simply "going through" the curriculum to guaranteeing the achievement of specific outcomes. This change means students are no longer just passive absorbers of information but active contributors to the learning journey. Teachers focus strongly on the hands-on application of theoretical knowledge and skills development, using various tasks and creative assignments like street theatre and short film production to encourage a more practical understanding of concepts.

Outcome-Based Education (OBE) introduces a fresh, distinct approach to teaching. Unlike traditional methods that broadly cover a subject, OBE focuses on transmitting precise knowledge specific to a student's learning needs. In the conventional model, teachers present information, and students accept it without question. However, OBE empowers students to engage with and present

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their perspectives on the subject matter, fostering a dynamic learning environment. Unlike the textbook-centric traditional model, OBE promotes active learning.” (Participant T1)

“The OBE-based pedagogical approach, with its core focus on achieving specific outcomes, necessitated the integration of diverse teaching methods into our daily lectures. It wasn't merely about conveying information as in traditional lecturing but involved conducting a variety of activities and tasks to assess students' attainment of the intended outcomes. This marked a significant change from our usual teaching methods.” (Participant T12)

“Traditional teaching methods heavily emphasized content and theoretical knowledge. The shift to OBE provided students with a platform to hone their skills and gain knowledge in a targeted manner. It afforded them the autonomy to express themselves freely, grasp the purpose and core content of their studies, and importantly, apply theoretical concepts to practical, real-life situations.” (Participant T9)

Several teachers have indicated a higher dependence on IT-enabled tools and visual media in the OBE curriculum. This shift towards technology in teaching has diversified instructional methods and enhanced the overall learning experience. The OBE curriculum has created an environment that encourages critical thinking and self-guided learning. Teachers claimed that students are more involved in self-study, independently researching topics, and thinking creatively, marking a departure from rote learning towards a more inquisitive, autonomous learning process. They also mentioned that each module now has a specific outcome to be achieved, providing a clear direction for both teaching and learning. The move to OBE has instigated changes in student assessment, focusing on academic scores and students' skills and comprehension.

Students Perspectives

The students perceived the shift to Outcome-Based Education as a move towards more outcome-focused, interactive, self-driven, and learner-centric teaching methods, with increased use of technology and a stronger real-world relevance. Despite initial difficulties in adaptation, students generally found the new teaching method to be more effective and engaging than the traditional method.

“The shift to Outcome-Based Education (OBE) has greatly altered our teaching methods. Traditional approaches tended to revolve around textbook recitation and interpretation, but with the introduction of OBE, the emphasis is on achieving specific learning outcomes. Exams are poorly based on outcomes” (Participant 1)

“Teachers now focus on providing real-life business case studies. The quality of our answers isn't solely based on the taught material but also incorporates real-life examples. This nuanced focus helps us relate our learning to the practical world. The previous teacher-centric approach displayed a stark absence of collaborative and group learning. Teachers would lecture, and students would

simply absorb information. In contrast, OBE emphasizes interactive and communal learning, fostering a richer educational environment." (Participant 8)

According to the students, the major shift brought about by OBE is a focus on learning specific outcomes rather than studying an entire subject. The learning process was perceived to be easier as it is centred on mastering key outcomes. The students observed a shift from a lecture-based teaching approach to a more self-study system with the introduction of OBE. They noted an increase in activities that foster independent learning and application of theories in a practical manner. Students reported increased use of ICT tools in the teaching process, indicating a move towards a more technologically enhanced and interactive learning environment under the OBE curriculum. Many students found the OBE system more explorative, as it encourages applying theories learned in the classroom to real-world scenarios. The traditional recitation and memorisation approach was replaced with a more practical understanding of the subject matter.

"As the traditional method of teaching is teacher-centric, it shows lack of collaboration and "In traditional teaching, teachers would adhere to a set syllabus, primarily teaching from textbooks or study materials. However, under the OBE system, teachers have adopted more dynamic methods, such as presentations, role plays, and interactive sessions to cover the syllabus. OBE allows us to choose our study focus and determine our activities. It tailors to our strengths and weaknesses and allows us time to learn and grow." (Participant 11)

Students reported that teachers under the OBE curriculum focused more on providing real-life business case studies and looked for answers based on taught content and real-life examples. This real-world relevance was seen as a significant shift from the traditional method of teaching. Students found the OBE system more interactive compared to the traditional teacher-centric approach. The new methods include presentations, role plays, and other interactive methods facilitating active student participation, leading to a collaborative and group learning atmosphere. Students perceived OBE as more learner-centric as compared to the traditional method. In their view, traditional education was overly focused on what was being taught rather than what the students actually learned. A few students shared that adapting to the OBE system was initially challenging. However, over time, they were able to adjust, even though a bit of hesitation might still be present.

Change in Activities and Assignments

Teachers Perspectives

Outcome-Based Education (OBE) has dramatically transformed the way educational activities and assignments are designed and executed to create a more engaging, hands-on, and relevant learning experience. These modifications encourage creativity, deepen understanding, and facilitate real-world application of knowledge, ensuring tasks are tied directly to specific learning outcomes. Education under OBE extends beyond just absorbing information; it also focuses on cultivating skills and competencies that equip students for their future work-life and life beyond school. Nowadays, assignments incorporate practical applications, giving students an opportunity to tackle real-world issues and gain a comprehensive

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understanding of their subjects. As a result, these tasks and activities have become more meaningful, being directly connected to accomplishing certain learning outcomes.

“OBE is fundamentally activity-oriented. Students have the opportunity to put their learning into practice through activities and assignments. This hands-on approach offers them insights into potential challenges in their respective fields. Assignments under OBE are not just paper-based but encompass a range of tasks, including organizing events, producing short films, and taking online courses such as those offered on Edx. These varied learning experiences holistically contribute to both their personal and professional development.” (Participant T4)

“Traditional activities often seemed perfunctory, but OBE-based assignments enable deeper comprehension of the subject matter. These assignments challenge students to explore and learn more, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical applications. Unlike traditional tasks that could be completed with just a pen and paper, OBE assignments necessitate creative student engagement, emphasizing quality over quantity.” (Participant T5)

“The introduction of the OBE curriculum revolutionized the nature and structure of activities and assignments. Previously, tasks primarily focused on building subject knowledge, but OBE assignments also emphasize real-world applications. Consequently, students better understand the purpose and relevance of their learning.” (Participant T11)

Teachers have noticed a clear move towards incorporating real-life applications in OBE's tasks and assignments. These assignments are crafted to gauge students' understanding of theoretical knowledge and their capability to apply it in real-life situations. The objective isn't to endorse mere memorisation but to promote a deeper comprehension of concepts. This shift has made education more relevant to industries, fostering entrepreneurial traits and preparing students effectively for their future careers.

Students Perspectives

The shift to the Outcome-Based Education system has led to significant changes in the nature of activities and assignments. The changes in the educational system are now emphasising collective activities, results-oriented tasks, the application of theories, and individual learners taking charge of their education. Even though there were a few challenges initially, students see these modifications as beneficial, encouraging a more engaging, hands-on, and personalised learning experience.

“We, as students, have the flexibility and freedom to learn in our preferred ways. It's an array of learning methodologies, not a single path. It reduces peer comparison as each of us is targeting unique outcomes. Under OBE, there's a clear articulation of what we students are expected to learn and do. We better understand our required skills and knowledge, allowing us to adjust our focus and inquiries more effectively.” (Participant 2)

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Students have noted a notable shift from solo assignments to more collaborative tasks. in the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) program. Such cooperative projects foster team spirit and collective problem-solving and are also deemed by the students as more engrossing and thought-provoking. OBE's essence lies in its target on the predetermined learning outcomes for each course, steering clear from the conventional rote learning of the entire subject content. This paves the way for assignments to break the mould of traditional formats. In the OBE system, students are often entrusted with eclectic tasks like curating short films or delving into role-playing exercises. These activities are lauded by students as they immerse them into real-world scenarios, prompting them to don multiple hats and analyze the subject from various perspectives. Such hands-on experiences deepen their comprehension of the subject and hone their practical skills, thereby enriching learning and enjoyable.

"Before OBE, most of my assignments felt like routine tasks. We'd get a topic, delve into our textbooks, memorize, and regurgitate. But with OBE, the shift is palpable. Recently, in our literature course, we were grouped into teams and asked to produce a short film interpreting a scene instead of writing a typical essay on Shakespeare's 'Macbeth'. The whole experience was transformative. I collaborated closely with my peers, which was a learning curve—negotiating ideas, understanding different perspectives, and collectively bringing a vision to life. and then, the act of transforming literature into a visual medium demanded that we truly understand the depth and nuances of the play. It wasn't about rote memorization anymore but comprehension, interpretation, and creativity. I genuinely believe assignments like these don't just teach us the subject, they prepare us for the real world – teaching us collaboration, critical thinking, and hands-on problem-solving." (Participant 1)

"Assignments under OBE have become more creative and aligned with the desired outcomes. We now create short films, role-plays, and other interactive materials facilitating active learning. The transition to OBE has led to a decline in the pass percentage. Many students and teachers still struggle with approaching and evaluating OBE exams." (Participant 9)

The OBE program allows students more autonomy in determining what they wish to study and how they wish to learn, signifying a transition towards a more student-driven, tailored educational approach. This curriculum emphasizes applying theories practically instead of just parroting them, resulting in a more student-focused, hands-on learning experience. The emphasis is on what the students should learn and be able to accomplish. However, some students have found the application-focused assignments challenging, highlighting the need for additional support and guidance during this change in teaching approaches.

Change in exams, marks & evaluation pattern

Teachers Perspectives

Outcome-Based Education (OBE) has dramatically changed the landscape of the examination system, the grading pattern, and the overall evaluation process. This approach encourages a deeper grasp of subjects and promotes practical applications of theories, making the learning process more engaging and meaningful for students. This comprehensive method seems to elevate education quality and boost student performance, evident by the increased passing rates. Examinations in the OBE system aim to understand whether students

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have met the intended learning outcomes instead of simply testing their memorisation skills. The questions challenge students' abilities to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world situations instead of merely recalling concepts. The grading in OBE isn't easy; it requires students to put in significant effort to achieve high scores. Both internal and external evaluations have specific passing scores. Some educators have pointed out that while the bar for passing isn't too high, getting top marks demands considerable work.

"Examinations under OBE have evolved into learning activities rather than just memory tests. Students understand that their ability to achieve intended outcomes is being assessed. Creative responses to case-based questions have become standard, narrowing the gap between academia and industry. Evaluation under OBE, though more time-consuming due to its comprehensive nature and inclusion of more rubrics, seems to have resulted in a higher pass rate as students engage more deeply with the learning process." (Participant T3)

"The question pattern has undergone a significant transformation, moving away from direct 'what' and 'how' questions to those focusing on practical applications. The focus has moved from textbook-based direct questions to those requiring the application of knowledge. This change has enhanced the quality of questions and, consequently, shifted the evaluation pattern...The OBE curriculum makes it easier for students to pass but harder to score high marks. This shift benefits students' future careers, equipping them with the practical skills and understanding needed for success." (Participant T6)

Teachers also emphasise that language proficiency and regular attendance have become more important under OBE. Overall, there seems to be a consensus among teachers that the pass rates have increased since OBE was introduced. This rise in pass rates could be due to the shift in the examination and evaluation system, which now prioritises understanding and practical application of knowledge over rote memorisation. Some teachers also report that students need to dedicate more effort under the OBE system. Success in exams is directly tied to students' effort, leaving no room for passive learning or rote memorisation.

Students Perspectives

The new assessment approach is something students have taken notice of. The emphasis now lies on the students' understanding and practical application of the course content, steering away from a mere rote-learning of the material. While some view this updated methodology as being more considerate of individual learning preferences and as potentially enhancing pass rates, others perceive it as complicating the attainment of higher grades.

"The evaluation process now aligns with the achievement of expected outcomes. Exams entirely revolve around outcome-related questions, which allow us to apply the theories we've studied. The pass percentage for theoretical subjects has seen a considerable increase. Teachers now grade based on the quality of our answers, not just how closely we stick to provided theories." (Participant 5)

"Competency-based questions can range from case-study questions, multiple-choice questions, to source-based integrated questions. The goal is to alleviate pressure on students who find traditional

participation challenging. As students, we now have a platform to express our opinions, which can significantly enrich our learning if teachers analyze these insights and provide constructive feedback. This engagement can enhance each student's quality of education." (Participant 6)

This innovative evaluation system grades students based on their comprehension and implementation of course content instead of simply recollecting and regurgitating theoretical aspects. It encompasses various types of questions, including case studies, multiple-choice, and integrated source-based ones, aiming to alleviate the stress associated with exams. However, not all students have easily adapted to this new academic structure. Some are concerned that pass rates might dip due to unfamiliarity with these novel testing and grading techniques. On the other hand, some students view this system as being more comprehensive and meticulous, promoting a deeper understanding and practical application of the coursework.

Change in quality of education

Teachers Perspectives

The introduction of Outcome-Based Education (OBE) has significantly transformed the educational landscape. OBE has positively influenced educational quality by shifting away from rote memorisation towards a greater emphasis on understanding and applying theories, championing hands-on and technical knowledge, and enhancing various skills. However, its impact will only become apparent as more student's graduate having been educated under this system.

Several teachers have noted that OBE encourages shifting from theoretical learning to a more hands-on, technical approach. They suggest that this focus on practical knowledge is timely and contributes to students' holistic personal and professional growth. They've also noticed an improvement in the Teaching Learning Evaluation (TLE) system with OBE, with a more directed and meaningful effort stemming from the mapping of Program Outcomes (PO), Program Specific Outcomes (PSO), and Course Outcomes (CO) across all educational activities and assessments.

A number of teachers have noted that the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) approach fosters more dynamic classroom interactions, stimulating robust discussions on diverse subjects. This encourages learners to stretch beyond the confines of textbook wisdom and immerse themselves in hands-on learning, facilitating a richer comprehension of theoretical concepts. The OBE curriculum's focus on accomplishing Course Outcomes (COs) has enhanced several student capabilities, including analytical thinking, communication, teamwork, and language skills. Moreover, the curriculum's endorsement of research cultivates a deep-rooted understanding of academic disciplines.

As per certain teachers, OBE gives students the autonomy to map out their own learning journeys, adapt to their strengths and limitations, and allocate ample time for mastering their subjects. This degree of flexibility is perceived as a significant empowerment tool for learners. The consensus among most educational professionals is that OBE has elevated the standard of education. They point out that this systematic

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approach encourages out-of-the-box thinking and promotes research, leading to an in-depth understanding of subjects. However, one teacher remarked that the full impact of this shift on the quality of education is yet to be completely understood.

“The introduction of the OBE curriculum has enhanced the quality of education where the students and teachers are learning together and sharing ideas. The focus on outcome has shifted the idea of learning things to gain marks to learn things to understand them only then could it be applied to real-life scenarios such as using case study solving etc. If guided on the right path, this kind of education moulds better and more reliable future generations with knowledge and values. The involvement of students in this OBE curriculum is huge and that's a positive side of it.” (Participant T2)

“OBE empowers students to choose what they would like to study and how they would like to study it. Not only does it adapt to a learner's strengths and weaknesses, but it also provides sufficient time to attain proficiency and fluency in the subject matter. They focus on the outcome of your actions, rather than how you feel about performing your tasks. Outcome-based goals tend to be easier to quantify. For this reason, most people focus on making outcome-based goals.” (Participant T7)

I am not sure about that any quality of education changed in OBE curriculum. The thing which I felled was that all goes in a systematic way which helped students more. Students started thinking outside the box and researching more, enlarging deep knowledge in a particular subject.” (Participant T9)

Students Perspectives

Students perceive that implementing the OBE curriculum has significantly elevated the standard of education. The pedagogical paradigm has transitioned from an instructor-focused methodology to a student-oriented one, fostering an environment for students to articulate their ideas more openly and apply their knowledge in a tangible, outcome-oriented fashion. Nevertheless, a segment of students expresses the desire for a more structured system implementation. Despite certain obstacles, the overall agreement points towards this change harbouring the ability to render education more pertinent, engaging, and advantageous for learners.

“Outcome-based education (OBE) places us, the students, at the heart of the educational system. It's not about how we achieve the end result but what we're expected to achieve. OBE allows for a more flexible, relaxed and personalised learning experience that is poorly depends on the application in a real-life context.” (Participant 4)

The OBE curriculum, by fostering an environment where students can express their views, can further augment their personal growth and values, provided teachers adequately assess and rectify their insights. While the OBE curriculum has undeniably enhanced the educational quality, students underscore the need for a structured approach in its implementation to reap maximum benefits. The conventional rote learning method has been supplanted by a more enriched knowledge-centric curriculum, promoting student creativity.

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The OBE curriculum prioritises a learner-centric approach, aiding students in gaining a deeper comprehension of concepts and emphasising the importance of the learning process, not just the subject matter being taught.

"Outcome-based education (OBE) places us, in a comfortable position. It's not about how we achieve the end result but what we're expected to achieve. OBE allows for a more flexible and personalised learning experience. The focus is on students achieving our learning goals by the end of the educational process. OBE enables continuous tracking and measurement of our performance, allowing for constant growth and improvement." (Participant 10)

"When I was researching universities, I noticed that the OBE system, which is quite popular in foreign institutions, has now made its way to Indian universities as well. This instantly drew my attention. The shift from merely focusing on the educational process to emphasizing what students should ideally demonstrate upon course completion really stands out. It's not just about textbooks anymore; it's about cultivating professional skills, values, and attitudes that will be valuable in real-world scenarios." (Participant 3)

The adoption of the Outcome-Based Education (OBE) system by Indian universities, a model previously established in foreign academic institutions, has ostensibly enhanced their allure for the student populace. What distinguishes OBE is its emphasis on tangible outcomes that a student is expected to manifest upon course completion. This encompasses not merely academic acumen but also extends to professional skills, moral values, attitudes, and capabilities. This paradigm shift from an exclusive focus on the pedagogical process to actual outcomes implies that the purview of learning is not restricted to conventional study materials; it transcends them.

"The quality of education under the OBE system feels elevated. Instead of merely relying on traditional materials, there's an expansion of knowledge that prepares us for the future. It's refreshing to see the approach transition from just subject-specific outcomes to broader, cross-curricular results that align with our anticipated roles in society and our professional life. One thing I genuinely appreciate about OBE is its commitment to tracking and measuring our performance continuously. It's not just about the end result; every step of our educational journey is mapped and assessed. This consistent check ensures we are on the right path, and it feels like a more holistic approach to education, keeping us aligned with our long-term goals." (Participant 5)

OBE's appeal lies in its futuristic approach. Instead of being confined to subject-specific outcomes, it ventures into long-term, interdisciplinary outcomes that align closely with the roles students will assume in their subsequent professional and personal lives. An inherent aspect of OBE is its commitment to monitoring and gauging student performance. By emphasizing outcomes, the system continually evaluates students' progress, ensuring they are consistently aligned with their learning objectives and are equipped for future challenges.

Perception on best method of education

Teachers Perspectives

Most teachers strongly preferred Outcome-Based Education, highlighting its advantages in fostering critical thinking, promoting student engagement, developing essential skills, and its outcome-centric approach. However, the extent of the changes required for its implementation might make some educators hesitant about fully embracing it. A vast majority of the teachers expressed their preference for the OBE teaching trend. They argued that OBE is better because it focuses on professional and technical knowledge application, real-world relevance of courses, student-centric evaluations, and the cultivation of industry-oriented skills. According to Bloom's taxonomy of learning, OBE was also seen as fostering higher-order thinking skills. Several teachers noted that OBE, unlike traditional education methods, nurtures critical and analytical thinking in students. This is increasingly valuable in the contemporary job market, where employers seek candidates who can think critically and analytically rather than those who simply reproduce learned information.

Several teachers highlighted student engagement's role in OBE. In this trend, teaching is not a 'one-man show', but rather a collaborative process that involves discussions and idea-sharing, thereby promoting greater achievement in learning. It also allows for two-way communication and a healthier relationship between teachers and students. Teachers emphasised that OBE focuses on developing essential skills such as communication efficiency, language proficiency, teamwork, and a student's analysis capabilities. This holistic development was seen as a strong point in favour of OBE.

"In my years of teaching, I've seen various methodologies come and go, but the dynamism OBE brings to the classroom is truly unparalleled. You see, teaching is no longer just about standing in front of the class and delivering lectures. With OBE, I've noticed a tremendous spike in student participation. Our classes have transformed into thriving hubs of discussions, brainstorming, and collective problem-solving. It's not just about me talking and students listening anymore; it's a symbiotic relationship where both parties learn from each other. I must emphasize how this approach has remarkably enhanced essential skills in our students. I've witnessed significant improvements in their communication, their grasp over language nuances, and their teamwork during group projects. More importantly, their analytical skills have sharpened, allowing them to dissect problems and come up with solutions. OBE doesn't just focus on the 'what', it delves into the 'how', and that holistic development is something traditional methods can't easily replicate." (Participant T8)

Teachers noted that the outcome-centric approach of OBE helps students to not just learn theories but to understand what they can do after learning, thereby focusing on practical applications and demonstrations. This, in turn, empowers students to choose what and how they study and provides sufficient time to attain proficiency in the subject matter. Despite the overall preference for OBE, one teacher disagreed, preferring traditional teaching methods over OBE. The teacher voiced concerns about the large-scale changes that OBE demands, including abolishing exams and giving more weightage to assignments.

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“In my opinion OBE is always the better and best option. This is because, in traditional method, the teaching becomes a one man show, that is, the professor plays the role there. But in OBE, there is importance for everyone. There discussions take place and them all share ideas, which further leads to great level of achievements in learning.” (Participant T6)

“While I recognize and respect the merits of the Outcome-Based Education system, personally, I find myself gravitating more towards our traditional teaching methods. My main concern with OBE is the monumental shift it necessitates in our educational structure. Abolishing examinations, for instance, is a drastic measure. Exams, in my view, are more than just tests of memory; they are tools that evaluate a student's ability to comprehend, process, and apply knowledge under pressure. By placing excessive emphasis on assignments, I fear we might be overlooking other crucial aspects of a student's development. I've been teaching for over two decades, and I've observed firsthand the multifaceted benefits of our time-tested methods. While I'm open to incorporating some elements of OBE, I do hold reservations about entirely adopting it as our primary pedagogical model.” (Participant T7)

Students Perspectives

While some students favour OBE or traditional teaching methods, many prefer a mix of both to leverage the advantages of each. The integration of technology and outside-classroom learning also emerges as an influential trend. The practical application and clear learning objectives in the OBE method have significantly contributed to its perceived effectiveness. Some students perceive Outcome-Based Education (OBE) as a more apt and relaxed form of learning, enhancing knowledge and creativity and improving soft skills. Some students find value in the traditional curriculum as it gives them space to learn about the subject in detail. The traditional way of teaching theory was also mentioned as an effective approach.

“I think including technology in the OBE curriculum has expanded learning beyond the classroom. It's made the learning environment more interactive and livelier. Through e-books and other digital resources, we can access enriched content featuring videos, augmented reality, and audio files.” (Participant 5)

Many students advocated for a blended approach, drawing upon the benefits of both traditional and OBE (Outcome-Based Education) teaching methods. Direct quotes from students indicate a desire to learn theoretical concepts traditionally, while also integrating practical insights from OBE. One student emphasized the role of modern technology in enhancing education. They pointed out how mobile devices and digital interactivity have not only enlivened the learning process but have also extended educational experiences beyond the four walls of a classroom. This advancement is evident in the incorporation of multimedia elements, such as videos, augmented reality, and audio files, into the curriculum.

“In my opinion, there's undeniable value in the way traditional methods explain theory – it's systematic, structured, and gives a strong foundation. But when it comes to real-world applications, the hands-on approach of OBE makes a huge difference. Think of it this way: If the traditional

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method tells us the 'what,' then OBE shows us the 'how.' I've also been amazed at the role technology plays in making lessons more engaging. With the aid of my smartphone and various interactive apps, I'm not just stuck with books. I can watch videos that break down complex topics, use augmented reality tools to visualize abstract concepts, and even listen to audio lectures on the go. Merging these methods truly gives us the best of both worlds." (Participant 8)

"For me, the combination of traditional and OBE is like blending the best parts of past and present educational techniques. While I appreciate the depth of understanding that the traditional method offers, the practical emphasis in OBE makes the learning tangible and relevant. Also, we can't ignore the digital age we're in. Learning is no longer confined to classrooms and textbooks. Mobile-based resources and digital content, like augmented reality and multimedia, have changed the game. I've personally benefited from course materials embedded with videos and other multimedia—it's a refreshing change from just reading text." (Participant 10)

Furthermore, students expressed a high regard for the practicality OBE offers, enabling them to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world situations. The clear, defined learning objectives that the OBE model presents are particularly appreciated by students. They value the clarity provided by understanding the anticipated outcomes at the onset, offering them a well-defined roadmap of the course's objectives.

"There's something very reassuring about the traditional method of teaching – the structured pace, the exhaustive coverage of theories. But, when it's time to translate that theory into action, OBE steps in perfectly. I can't stress enough how beneficial it's been to have a clear set of outcomes to aim for in each module. It's like having a roadmap for your learning journey. And talking about the digital revolution in education, it's a blessing! With mobile devices, I feel I have an entire library and a world of interactive experiences in my pocket. It's more dynamic, more immediate. The inclusion of videos and AR tools, for instance, makes learning not just efficient, but also enjoyable." (Participant 12)

Discussion

The introduction of Outcome-Based Education (OBE) marks a paradigm shift in the pedagogical arena, transitioning from traditional teacher-centric methods to a more student-focused, outcome-driven model. The teachers are acutely aware of this transformation, emphasizing the shift towards meeting specific learning goals as opposed to merely progressing through a predetermined curriculum, the current findings aligns with Babu & Roy (2023) and Alam et al. (2022). This evolution fosters a more dynamic learning environment, notably enriched with the integration of technology, IT tools, and visual media into teaching. Moreover, the emphasis on fostering critical thinking, promoting self-driven learning, and underscoring the practical application of knowledge sets OBE distinctly apart from conventional rote memorization-centric methods (Peng et al., 2009; Babu & Joseph, 2022). While the merits are significant, the challenges accompanying such a profound change are equally daunting, necessitating resilience, adaptability, and adequate resources for educators (Botha, 2002; Killen, n.d). However, it's vital to recognise and address the apprehensions surrounding the extensive changes necessitated by this approach.

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Students' perceptions of OBE echo those of educators. Student preferences vary between OBE and conventional methodologies, with many advocating for a blended approach (Pang et al., 2009). They suggest that they appreciate its outcome-oriented, engaging, and learner-centric characteristics, a sentiment corroborated by Babu & Joseph (2023). They display a marked preference for active participation and value the relevance of their studies to real-world scenarios. However, as Norman (2009) noted, the transition to this innovative system has been challenging for some, revealing a need for enhanced support during the adaptation phase. OBE's experiential learning emphasis is evident in teachers' feedback. They highlight the curriculum's shift towards assignments that directly mirror specific learning outcomes, emphasizing real-world applicability. As current study suggests, this transformation embodies the broader pedagogical revolution championed by OBE — one that accentuates creativity, innovation, and real-world applications (Botha, 2002; Killen, n.d). However, the full potential of this shift can only be realized with the provision of robust support mechanisms and resources.

A notable facet of the OBE transition is the evolution of the grading system. Sullivan & Downey (2015) assert that this new assessment landscape prioritizes understanding and the application of knowledge over rote memory. While teachers generally perceive increased pass rates with OBE's introduction, students' reactions are mixed, pointing towards potential challenges in navigating this novel grading structure (Sakata et al., 2022). Furthermore, the current research and insights from Asim et al.'s study (2021) indicate that OBE is heralding enhanced educational quality. With its departure from pure rote learning towards fostering deeper understanding and knowledge application, the Teaching Learning Evaluation (TLE) system reforms and the focus on Course Outcomes (COs) are undeniable indicators of progressive change. However, with all its apparent benefits, OBE also surfaces reservations and apprehensions. The magnitude of the changes it demands can be overwhelming for some. This study's findings suggest that while OBE offers numerous advantages, including bolstering critical thinking and amplifying student engagement, addressing the associated challenges is imperative (Nirmala, n.d; Botha, 2002; Killen, n.d; Pang et al., 2009).

The findings from this study carry profound implications for the educational sector. The transition to Outcome-Based Education (OBE) can fundamentally reshape how educators approach teaching and how students experience learning. By emphasizing specific outcomes, there's a significant shift towards real-world applicability and critical thinking. This alignment could bridge the existing gap between academic instruction and industry or real-world requirements, ultimately producing graduates better equipped for their forthcoming professional challenges (Patnaik & Paas, 2023). Furthermore, the evident integration of technology suggests that modern educational environments can become more adaptive and responsive to the ever-evolving societal and technological trends. However, every research endeavor comes with its set of constraints, and this study is no exception. One limitation is the sample size and diversity; the study might not fully represent all educational settings or regions. Experiences and perceptions of those involved in OBE can differ based on cultural, socioeconomic, and institutional variables. The temporal scope of the study is another limitation. Given that OBE is a relatively novel concept, this system's sustainability and long-term effects remain to be seen. The current research provides a snapshot, but the constantly evolving nature of education suggests that perceptions and effectiveness could shift with time. Moreover, while efforts were

made to garner objective data, teacher and student feedback inherently contains personal biases and perceptions, which might not always align with the broader reality.

Considering these findings, several suggestions emerge. Given the monumental shift in teaching approach inherent in OBE, there's an evident need for continuous professional development programs tailored for educators. Such initiatives would furnish them with the methodologies and skills essential for OBE's successful implementation. Recognizing the challenges some students face adapting to this new format, educational institutions should ramp up their support structures. These might encompass mentoring programs, supplementary resources, or specialized counselling services. In addition, considering students' diverse inclinations, it might be beneficial to explore a blended approach. This approach would combine the virtues of traditional teaching methodologies with the principles underpinning OBE, potentially offering a more inclusive and adaptable educational experience.

Therefore, longitudinal studies are essential to track students' and educators' outcomes and experiences over extended periods. Such research would provide insights into OBE's sustainability and its long-term ramifications. With the emphasis on technology, deeper investigations into how various tech tools and platforms can be seamlessly integrated into OBE are warranted. International comparative studies on OBE's implementation and outcomes across different countries would also be invaluable, offering a global perspective on best practices, challenges, and potential opportunities. Lastly, since OBE prides itself on real-world applicability, feedback from industry stakeholders regarding the skills and preparedness of OBE graduates could be instrumental. Such feedback can be the linchpin for refining the system, ensuring it remains tethered to real-world exigencies. Transition to OBE, the ever-changing educational landscape necessitates unceasing exploration, evaluation, and evolution. The transformative potential of OBE is undeniable, but its triumph hinges on persistent research, feedback, and refinement. This study hopes to influence positive change within education, championing a system that prioritises student growth, engagement, and real-world applicability.

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